

TECHNIQUE TO ATTAIN SUSTAINABILITY IN GENDER-BASED SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP: A FOCUS ON NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11199513>

Abstract

Non-governmental organizations have become imperative to human existence and perform a major role in the inclusion and accessibility to economic, environmental and social equity. Particularly, the objectives are, to: dissect government policies and legislations that enable public participation of NGOs in social problem-solving in Nigeria; and explore the efforts of NGOs as a social agent in assisting the vulnerable people in the communities to overcome social challenges. This investigation is a qualitative approach that makes use of an open-ended structured instrument. It adopted a purposive non-probability sampling technique to ascertain the key experts. Note-taking and participants' observation were deployed to complement voice recording. The study made use of five discussants, this was given a nod by (Nyumba, Wilson, Derrick, & Mukherjee, 2018). The recorded session was transcribed accordingly. The data collected was themed, categorized and analyzed. The study revealed that there is access for NGOs to publicly participate in solving the social problem. The efforts of the free services have led to an increased standard of living for the vulnerable and disadvantaged, and job creation. It was concluded that the female gender dominated the humanitarian services. The study, therefore, recommended more social agent participation in social arrangement and engagement. The male gender is encouraged to participate in humanitarian services.

Keywords: Volunteer, Sustainable development, Non-governmental organizations, Free service, Social agent.

INTRODUCTION

There are three components of sustainability (environment, economic and social equity). Mostly, community engagement can be used in place of social equity, and that tempo will be maintained in this

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study. Social equity includes access to housing, logistics and transportation, job availability, inclusive education, recreation and cultural life, peoples' enablement to fully participate in politics (vote and be voted for), and, solving societal problems in the community. In solving the problems, NGOs have successfully become the bridging gap over the decades for the citizens, residents and communities to access the components of social equity.

Connecting the built environment and socio-economic activity with nature's restrictions and opportunities is necessary for sustainability (Durana et al., 2015). Meeting both existing and future demands by striking a balance among three factors (preserving a just and healthy society, safeguarding the environment, and promoting social equity—this is central to this study). These elements are linked and are critical to building a sustainable community. Social equity (SE) refers to the ability of citizens to actively engage in the cultural and political lives of the community, as well as to have fair and equal access to housing, employment, transportation, education, and leisure activities. It is strongly related to the two major sustainability pillars of environmental preservation and economic viability. It relies on regional support, a diversified economy that offers a variety of employment and volunteering possibilities for adults of all backgrounds and skill levels as well as a healthy environment with clean water and air, open places for recreation, and safety from imminent threats (Chico Sustainability, 2021). Ensuring there is enough shelter for people of all ages and income levels, fostering a transparent government that respects public opinion, honouring arts and cultures, supporting the development and preservation of complete neighbourhoods, aiding the most vulnerable community members, and fostering community health by protecting from risks and offering a secure multimodal circulation system are just a few of the techniques in the framework that promote social equity. The genealogical background of social entrepreneurship is traceable to the 19th century (Rahdari et al., 2016). Over the past four decades, in a wide range of industries, the concept of (SE) social entrepreneurship has both developed and gained popularity (Rey-Mart, Ribeiro-Soriano, & Palacios-Marqués, 2016). Social Entrepreneurship (SE) has a huge positive influence on the quality of life for people in both developed and underdeveloped nations (Adeyeye, 2016).

It was reported that there are significant disparities among the best social entrepreneurship programmes, where between 32% and 42% of fellowships are given to women by the Schwab Foundation for SE, Ashoka, and the Skoll World Forum (Carty, 2020), this is not an exemption to in Nigeria. The field of entrepreneurship has come to stay like other age-long disciplines. It has her areas of specialization such as techno-preneurship, education, social knowledge-based, and political among others. Aside from this, the field has attributes in virtually other pursuits. NGO as a term emanated in 1945, in the operations of the United Nations (UN), this was used to refer to some of the first non-state organisations (the under-

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developed nations) that were given advisory status in the operations of the UN. On the level of development, humanitarian efforts, human rights, and many other dimensions of public operations, NGOs are the primary third sector (Adeyeye, 2016) of any economy. The phenomenal popularity and growth of NGOs in Nigeria, and the corresponding dominancy of female social entrepreneurs among other social ills call for an investigation into the attainability of sustainability of such. Generally, donors, parent organisations, grants, endowments, subsidies, contributions, and fees are sources of funding for NGOs (Adeyeye, 2016; Ngeh, 2013; Ogunyemi & Fakolujo, 2012). NGOs form core areas of economic, political, cultural, and social activity, together with the market and the state (Marley, 2015).

Nigeria is a nation full of neglect and rejection by the inhumane democratic political system, of higher and middle-income earners. The population characteristics of the country have been coerced to be entrepreneurially inclined rather than passion and dreams, due to the harsh economy, the alarming rate of unemployment, religious bigotry and, cultural diversity. The nation has been in the highest insecurity dimension in history (banditry, herdsmen slaughtering, Boko-haram, money rituals, IPOB and Oodua Nations' agitators). All these have preceded the social entrepreneurs and NGOs to come in the gap for the disadvantaged (widows, children, internally displaced persons and the vulnerable). The study sees the roles NGOs are playing in the welfare of society as sacrosanct to collective social welfare and development.

By reality and default, government at all levels are considered the key player in policy across strata inclusive of social welfare. It is not an exaggeration to submit that the government alone is the mover and shaker of social change (Adibe & Obiefuna, 2012). The bulk of the problems of communities and community development are orchestrated by the inactions of the ruling class or government or simply put, the apathy of the stakeholders. NGOs as SE are booming in poor communities in championing the course of these problems (Diab, 2019). The essence of NGOs can't be underrated in any primitive and contemporary society, especially in developing nations where governments have failed to meaningfully play their roles and responsibilities to the citizens, residents and communities. (Adeyeye, 2016) subscribe to this, where economic and political systems have failed, a social entrepreneur may have the vision and will to use entrepreneurial behaviour for non-profit goals. Also, the insecurity menace, where millions of people have been displaced. The involvement of the NGO in giving helping hands to the government to solve societal problems has to an extent brought succor to the individuals and communities. The social agent of NGOs has numerically contributed to the well-being of the poor, and the well-to-do via health intervention, provision of sanitary pads, school bags, writing and reading materials, school uniforms, school sandals, public orientation and re-orientation among other laudable efforts. However, it's keenly noted that a particular gender dominates this circle.

The dominancy does not mean only one gender is in the business of social problem-solving. Also, authors have done research (Adeyeye, 2016; Moses & Maxwell, 2014; Ogunyemi & Fakolujo, 2012) on NGOs or social entrepreneurship combining other variables, but none have considered the technique to ascertain sustainability in gender-dominated social entrepreneurship and NGOs. It's on these premises that the study sought to investigate the technique to attain sustainability in gender-based social entrepreneurship with non-governmental organizations being central. Specifically, the research questions are: What are the government policies and legislations that enable public participation of your NGO in social problem-solving in Nigeria? What are the efforts of NGOs as social agents in assisting the vulnerable people in the communities to overcome social challenges?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Technique to Attain Sustainability (social equity)

In a time when social injustice and inequality engineered by certain elites become the norm, as it is in modern-day Nigeria, the idea of sustainability becomes a more complex one. Economic, ecological, and human factors are the three main facets of human existence that are discussed in terms of the sustainable development of society. The first element is crucial in that it establishes the tripod facets of human existence: biological, social collective and rational/psychological/spiritual (induced by internal traits, specific to one human being). The correlation between economic growth and environmental protection is a crucial aspect of the sustainable development strategy because the method of measuring economic growth solely by gross domestic profit GDP, without attempting to quantify the medium- and long-term benefits induced by environmental protection, is only a basic form and is not reasonable in sustainable development analysis. The human aspect of sustainable development is crucial because the concept of equality has many manifestations in connection to the sustainable development of human society (Durana et al., 2015). The principles of sustainable yield, sustainable society, and sustainable development all revolve around sustainability. A sustainable society is said to have figured out how to live within the restrictions set by ecological constraints. Sustainable development (SD) is a method of societal progress that successfully balances the requirements of the present and future generations with economic, social, and environmental factors (Meadowcroft, 2021). In the present day, SD is synonymous with sustainability.

Human as a Sub-set of Social Equity in the Sustainability

Assuming that workable substitutes have been found to preserve ecological harmony, authorities, quality of life, and labour standards for personal, professional, and/or social fulfilment (Dempsey et al., 2011). There wouldn't be a need for the player to consider human sustainability in terms of social interactions, relationships, societal norms, and ethical principles. A generation is preoccupied with preserving cultural

diversity, like the prevention or cure of social ills, such as loneliness or alienation, a lack of job satisfaction, relativism of values, the end of history, and future uncertainty or disease. This balance should be necessitated by the role of the human as a social agent. The following goals are the foundations upon which (Minica & Franț, 2008), the human aspect of SD are rooted: promotion of education, training, and public support for the environment; safeguarding and publicising human health; combating poverty; demographic threats to sustainable development (Durana et al., 2015). Bansal et al., (2019) demonstrated the relationship between sustainability and social entrepreneurship as innovation and technology adopted by social entrepreneurs, the contribution of social entrepreneurs to rural and community development, urbanisation, social, economic, and environmental implications of the social entrepreneurs, bankrolling and crowdfunding trends in the act of social enterprise, and female entrepreneurship.

Gender-Based Social Entrepreneurship (SE)

Since the 1990s, SE has been increasingly popular because some academics think it is a more economically viable way to generate social good (Marley, 2015). More than merely an even distribution of men and women in leadership positions contributes to the gender gap in SE. It also concerns the continued presence of patriarchy in our institutional structures and leadership paradigms (Carty, 2020). A times, the engagement of SE isn't about civil alone, it also captures commercial purposes depending on the mission and vision of such. NGOs, especially those in Nigeria, are one of the key forces behind SE worldwide. Small informal groups to substantial formal organisations make up the gamut of NGOs (Adeyeye, 2016), SE is one of the niches and branches of broad entrepreneurship, the endeavour of potentially explosive (non-financial) gains of advancing social good and addressing social needs via risk-taking innovations which requires a variety of chances, problems, ideas, and resources.

The term SE is only used to describe non-profit organisations that venture into earned-income or not-for-profit organisations to provide social value and effect change. They are consumed by the drive for a result that has a social impact rather than just financial gain (Adeyeye, 2016). Roper & Cheney, (2005), contend that the issues of who should and who can be responsible for the necessities of civil society are at the heart of any discussion of SE. In addition, ideological concerns about the survival and well-being of civil society, as opposed to the political and economic spheres, also surface. There are different definitions to which authors have defined SE, but this study aligns with, a branch of entrepreneurship that deals with the identification of opportunities for unsatisfied social needs of the general populace, mostly the disadvantaged, rather than commercial needs. This is accomplished by a non-profit organisation (NPO) that is not restricted to only domestic context bringing a fresh or improved process, distribution outlet, product, organisational methods, or new supply source of raw materials for activities that provide social value. Secondly, social entrepreneurship is the combination of innovativeness, creative thinking, critical thinking and motivation to solve social problems. Mthembu & Barnard, (2019) defined social entrepreneurship as a cutting-edge strategy for delivering goods and services that address fundamental human rights that go

unmet by governmental or commercial institutions. It should however be noted that where social entrepreneurship is mentioned, sustainability is core.

SE comprises developing, assessing, and exploring chances for social change that are brought about by visionary and fervently committed individuals (Abu-Saifan, 2012). This study stressed that involvement in SE or humanitarian services is the concern of male and female social entrepreneurs. This is far from the reality in this contemporary social association. Despite variations in definition, the primary motivation is to generate social benefit, which is demonstrated by innovation or the development of something new. NGO as SE should adopt a model that best mobilizes the resources required to address the social problem being addressed because the social problem is what drives SE in the first place, as it changes society, solves social issues, and makes society better (Mthembu & Barnard, 2019). Social entrepreneurs are characterized as people or private organizations who have a social vision and the capacity to create novel solutions to social issues in their local areas (Korosec & Berman, 2006; Mthembu & Barnard, 2019). Therefore, this study described social entrepreneurs in NGOs as passionate people in the same system that is depriving others of social welfare, the concerned social agent channels resources to social problems spotted, identified and searched. The concerned oppressed, respond and explore the problem-turned opportunities to make the lives of individuals, groups of individuals and society better. Diab, 2019; Martin & Osberg, (2007) ambitious, strategic, resultful, resourceful, mission and, vision have been identified as attributes of social entrepreneurs. This act spurred the humanitarian to strike a balance between pursuit (money) and rendering philanthropical services to do social justice to the oppression in the society. Furthermore, the study submitted that some NGOs existed with a combination of business and human service i.e. the proceeds from the enterprise are pumped into the NGO. Secondly, some NGOs existed purely on the premises of social concerns i.e. no money is coming from the circular or conventional business organization. Similarly, some NGOs are waxing stronger on the shoulders of local and international donors.

SE is a prospective means to empower men, develop local women and solve other social issues (Diab, 2019). For SEs, profitability is a goal but it is not the only one because profits are reinvested in the mission rather than dispersed to shareholders, creating a "double bottom line" for the enterprise (realizing financial and social returns) (Mthembu & Barnard, 2019). Three fundamental elements of social entrepreneurship are: recognizing opportunity; expanding a newly proposed social value to claim balance, and suffering reduced by developing a new stable balance to provide a successful future. These three elements all involve finding a stable but unfair balance that prevents, criticizes, or harms a group that does not have the tools to improve balance (Martin & Osberg, 2007). SE is thought to have the potential to address many of the world's social ills (Kenny, Haugh, & Fotaki, 2020) because there is a consensus that SE can enhance the

quality of life for humans on Earth (Barberá-Tomás, Castelo, De Bakker, & Zietsma, 2019) due to the rise in neglects, social injustices and environmental concerns (Cavalcanti, 2021). SE as a discipline in the entrepreneurship family focuses specifically on changing society, producing social value, addressing social issues, and enhancing society (Mthembu & Barnard, 2019). In advancing the course of SE, as an emerging subject of entrepreneurship, shows that life is more than just getting money i.e. solving society's problems faced by minorities and the majority (Adeyeye, 2016), most especially the disadvantaged.

The concept of titans dominated entrepreneurship between 50 and 100 years ago. Titan is the view of business and the concept of entrepreneurship that places a strong emphasis on maximising profits, or "pretty tough capitalism." These "entrepreneurs," who were titans in some commodities industries like steel, oil and gas, were at the fore of entrepreneurship but weren't always inventive. Just like the business empires of Dangote, Tony Enumelu etc. of Nigeria. Later, in the 1980s and 1990s, there was a greater propensity for the idea of innovation based on Schumpeter's theory of innovation, which emphasises novelty and originality. Steve Wozniak and Steve Jobs are giants, who founded Apple Computer and stood out as entrepreneurs who pushed the envelope. Apart from the desire to make money, they demonstrated that innovators may employ ideas, designs, fantastic goods, intense passion, and empathy to alter the world i.e. changing the norms to accommodate the less privileged. This is in tandem with the submission of Adeniyi, (2022) who noted that digital skills will lead to Nigeria's business growth and consequentially, enhance the nation's development through flair for humanity. Because life is more than just maximising profits, a pace was set so that business people might establish organisations to improve the world. From the business they start, an entrepreneur can assist the community on a social level (Adeyeye, 2016). Furthermore, this study argues that an individual (social entrepreneur) can establish an organization without necessarily being meant for business. Thus, a thin line was drawn between business turned NGO and completely orchestrated NGO. This claim is supported by the survey (Aliyeva, 2021). Embracing a goal to produce and maintain social value (not simply private value), recognising and tenaciously pursuing new possibilities to further that mission, and acting as a change agent in the social sector are core attributes of SE (Aliyeva, 2021). One of the onus questions begging for honest answers is "Is humanitarian or NGO work meant for a particular gender? Through the work of non-governmental organizations, SE has evolved into a means of addressing the social needs of the underprivileged (NGOs) (Adeyeye, 2016).

Non-Governmental Organizations

The term NGO is a contemporary word used to describe traditional concepts like philanthropic and community organizations that, in the modern era, have evolved into something more than just benevolent organizations and instead serve humanity. They frequently prefer to be called civil society or the civil rights

movement or humanitarian (Adibe & Obiefuna, 2012). To administer their operations, they frequently rely on volunteers, which presents a problem with worker turnover, particularly in growing economies where there is high unemployment and the standard of living for retirees is low (Adeyeye, 2016). The World Association of Non-Governmental Organizations (WANGO) is the global body for NGOs, the humanitarians use a variety of strategies to achieve their objectives, some operate alone, and others form coalitions. Some organise raucous, protests and demonstrations, while others favour calm diplomacy or sober instruction (Adibe & Obiefuna, 2012). NGOs from industrialised nations are referred to as northern NGOs (NNGOs), whereas those from less developed nations are referred to as southern NGOs (SNGOs). Each of these is guided by a social vision and mission (Adeyeye, 2016), but it's a different ball game in this case for NGOs as social entrepreneurship.

NGOs are not established to make money for the individual, having paid staff, volunteers, and participating in activities that bring in money, they do not share revenues or surpluses with their members or management. NGOs are independent, private, non-profit organizations with a focus on enhancing the quality of life for underprivileged individuals, it is selflessly motivated by enthusiasm. This indicates that they are created willingly, with voluntary engagement and a passion to shift directions. Since NGOs are fundamentally self-mandating and do not operate under the authority of any state or international organization, their existence and activities are extremely vulnerable to criticism, they have been under fire from all tiers of government. NGOs on the international level might become ungovernable and uncountable (Adibe & Obiefuna, 2012). The claim that NGOs speak for the voice of the people has frequently been contested, raising the question of whether they truly speak for the people or are only there to serve the personal interests of those who founded them.

The neglect and decline in the roles and responsibilities of government have led to a sporadic rise in the number of NGOs in Nigeria. WANGO corroborated this fact, where it mentioned that there are 1,094 in Nigeria (Kolesnik, 2017). The World Bank divided NGOs into two categories: operational NGOs, which focus on project development, and promotional NGOs, which are focused on raising awareness of a subject. They can be found in areas such as care and welfare, emerging health crises, education and training, community social issues, environmental issues, economic issues, problems affecting women and youth, community health promotion, problems affecting children, problems affecting internally displaced people, and community development etc (Adeyeye, 2016).

Theoretical Review

There is a need for theoretical backing that encompasses sound and theoretical paths in all aspects of letters, not only academic discourse (Aruleba 2019; Aruleba and Adediran 2022). One sociological theory that

attempts to explain social development in society as well as how values are communicated to members of the community and how they may change through coordinated and negotiated efforts is the symbolic interactionist position. It was also emphasised that culture is a result of interactions between individuals in their regular social relationships. Through these interactions, culture from a wider community is adapted to daily living, and occasionally new methods of doing things are created. On this terrain, humans are seen as active actors who may resist challenges and alter social structures rather than as passive by-products of the social system. Thus, this viewpoint explains that social actors are at play in the formulation and application of international law. Therefore, one of the powerful actors in the social imbalance is represented by NGOs. They constantly negotiate the system in the interest of the disadvantaged as agents, challenging its structures and upholding its ideals (Adibe & Obiefuna, 2012).

The theory of sustainability is generally affiliated with what is weak and strong. What must be sustained? solutions to that question are sometimes divided into two spectrums (strong and weak) (Jenkins, 2011). There are three views to the sustainability model economic, political and ecological. This study will only exclude the ecological model due to the nature of the investigation. Economic theories advocate for the preservation of opportunity, typically in the form of capital. The stakeholders should view sustainability as an investment challenge, where they must leverage the yields from the use of natural resources to create new chances of equal or greater value. The advancement of people's general freedom to live the kinds of lives they have good cause to cherish is made possible by human growth. This concept, with a tendency toward independence, emphasises going back to and honouring the distinctive values and customs of a community to enhance their general quality of life. This ideology is predicated on the idea that growth only succeeds when there is a strong dedication to the objectives of society or the individual, such as cultural preservation (Marley, 2015). This ideology combats social injustice and imbalance in society. The freedoms in this sense are political freedom, social opportunities, and economic facilities as enshrined in the components of sustainability.

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization, (2023).

Figure 1: Relational Model of NGO as SE

METHODOLOGY

The current inquiry adopted an exploratory research design. Nyumba et al., (2018) submitted that focus group discussion is meant to deepen one's comprehension of social concerns, (Aruleba et al. 2019; Flanagan et al. 2015) noted that this permits the expression of the discussants' feelings, emotions, views and avoids manipulation. It adopts a purposive non-probability sampling technique to ascertain the key experts (NGO owners) for the collection of soft/raw data (recorded discussion), of the online focus group. The authors' effort is in tandem with the usage of online data collection for focus groups (Abrams & Gaiser, 2017). Note-taking and participants' observation were deployed to complement voice recording, this was achieved by the usage of a research assistant. Hours of 1-2 were dedicated to the data collection. The study made use of five discussants who voluntarily showed participation out of the recruited eight, this sample size was given a nod by (Dworkin, 2012; Nyumba, Wilson, Derrick, & Mukherjee, 2018), which noted that a

minimum of five and a maximum of fifty is valid for qualitative study. However, (Boddy, 2016) made a case for one sample size as far as there is justification. (Malterud, Siersma & Guassora, 2016) suggested criteria for sufficient sample size: quality of dialogue, study's aim, strategy for analysis, use of established theory, and sample specificity, all of which this study has fulfilled. The interview guide (intercept interview) for data collection was sent to the discussants ahead of the exercise in other to make them aware and prepared. Approval and voluntary participation with the letter of consent and subject information sheet were sought. Authorization was taken from the letter of consent and intercept guide that the discussion will be recorded. The recorded session was transcribed accordingly. Content form of analysis was deployed in analyzing the collected data.

Figure 2: Methodological approach

Source: Authors' Conceptualization, (2023).

DATA ANALYSIS

An instrument containing only the discussants' socio-demographic characteristics was initially sent to the discussants in other to focus more on the research questions in the period of actual discussion of the online focus group. This was preceded by a letter of consent and a subject information sheet.

Reported Results

The report might be delivered in a narrative or point-by-point manner. By sharing the data with the study's participants, a procedure known as member checking, or participant validation was used to confirm the findings, boosting the report's or study's accuracy and credibility (Birt et al., 2016; Zairul, 2021), the narrative approach was adopted for this research. The data analysis is structured into three major headings (socio-demographic, government policies and regulations, and the social agent's efforts).

1. *Socio-Demographic Characteristics*

First Discussant: The owner of the registered GoldHeart Foundation (GHF) is a female by gender with four years of experience in Ekiti State where she operates and eight years of accumulated experience in

social engagement. The B.sc (Ed) holder has sixty volunteers in her organization. Donations are for financing the NGO. For the outreach campaigns, Individual donations, private organizations, and collaboration are patterns of sourcing for materials/equipment/relief materials/cloth and food distribution.

Second Discussant: Every Child is a Star Foundation (ECSF) is owned and operated by a female and Bachelor of Arts holder, operating from Abuja (FCT), with about two years of experience, managing her NGO and an accumulated seven years in the industry. The NGO has twenty volunteers' strengths. Donations by deeds, personal income, individuals, social media and corporate bodies are the core ways for financing the organization. While crowdfunding, family and friends, Individuals and social media platforms are means of sourcing relief materials meant for outreaches.

Third Discussant: A young and vibrant female owns the God's Treasure Foundation for children and women which is located in Oyo state, with about a year managing her NGO and two years of accumulated experience in domiciling in social activities. She possesses a Higher National Diploma in Community Health; personal means have been the source of financing the NGO. The organization is boosted with zero volunteers at present. Letter distribution is the organization's strength in sourcing materials/equipment/relief materials/cloth and food distribution for campaigns/outreach.

Fourth Discussant: Toarleb Foundation (TF) is an NGO operating from Osun state. It's being ruined and managed by a female who is an MSc holder. The NGO enjoys five years of management and ten years of accumulated experience of the owner: The NGO is boosted by fifty-five volunteers. The sources of financing the organization are self, family and friends, philanthropists, and well-wishers. The outreaches are achieved by letter distribution, leveraging personal relationships, and donations.

Fifth Discussant: Hope For Us Charity (HFUS) is an independent free service organization founded by a female B.Sc holder from Osun State. The humanitarian organization operate from Lagos and Oyo states. The charity has been in operation for three years with an accumulated ten years' experience of the founder. The HFUS has a reasonable number of volunteers for her outreaches and campaigns. Fundraising through the sales of products is the core source of financing for the NGO. The store or market (open and closed) is the major point of getting materials needed for the campaigns or outreaches.

Source: Researcher's Database, (2023).

Figure 3: Legal Status of the NGOs.

GHF was silenced about the legal status of her NGO, GTF has not been registered with the Ministry of Women's Affairs as well as Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC). The remaining have legal backing to the operations. This gives the three NGOs (HFUS, TF and ECSF) a free hand to operate without fear or favour.

2. Government Policies and Legislation that Enables Public Participation of NGOs in the Social Problems Solving in Nigeria

You will quite agree with the study that no individual, corporate entity or charity organization can dabble in public participation or social engagement without having followed the necessary rules and regulations guiding the conduct of NGOs in your state of operation.

Government Policies and legislations that relate to NGO's Social Engagement:

The five charity organizations explicitly stated that the policies and regulations relating to their social engagements are the child rights policy, gender-based violence policy, national gender-based policy, education gender-based policy, Young Alliance for Global Enforcement of Children and Human Rights, trafficking in persons (prohibition) law enforcement and administration, Ekiti sexual violence against children. Others are the Oyo state action plan for the elimination of child labour, punitive widowhood rites, girl-child education, rights of people with disabilities and, girl-child education.

Policies and Legislation that Cage or Silences Your Social Engagement:

The Goldheart Foundation, ECSF, Treasure Foundation and HFUS stated emphatically ‘policies that silence NGOs don't exist’ as major stakeholders in policy drafting and implementation. While TF noted that the silence-ness in her state of operation.

Disposition of Government Officials to Registration within the State of Operation:

The service to Humanity organizations mentioned the Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development as the ministry in charge of NGO operations. NGOs can relatively operate without registration with them. Registration fee ranges between ₦10,000-₦18000.

Disposition of Government Officials to NGOs’ Mission and Vision:

The free service organizations complement the efforts of the government. The NGO doesn't have a direct link with the government. Each regime has its agenda, so it's a matter of keying into its agenda. The NGO's vision and mission are always tailored towards the government's broad human services.

Disposition of Government Officials NGOs’ campaigns or outreaches:

There is mutual and timely respect from the government for the NGO's contributions to the development of society. Encouragement, seminars, training and incentives have been organized freely for the NGOs which show that the government places value on the operations of the charity organizations.

Fined for Violation of Relevant Government Law(s), Rule(s) and Regulation(s):

The foundations Goldheart, ECSF, Treasure Foundation, TF and HFUS are law-abiding charity organizations. The NGOs operate within the ambits of required laws, rules and regulations.

Withdrawn of NGOs’ Certificate:

It was expressly stated that at no point had the certificates of registration been withdrawn. This is in tandem with the above submission.

3. Efforts of the NGOs as Social Agents in Assisting the Vulnerable People in the Communities to Overcome Social Challenges

Based on years of experience in social entrepreneurship and the operation of NGOs:

NGO’s Strives and Impacts on the Disadvantaged (Girls, Boys, Adults, orphans, widows, widower and the Communities) in Addressing their Social Challenges:

The efforts of the foundations on boys, girls, caregivers, widows, and vulnerable populations. The foundations' impacts on the disadvantaged are the making of sanitary pads, educational support and psycho-social support. Through this, charity organizations strengthen the disadvantaged's economic prowess.

Procedures in Executing the Strives and Impacts on the Disadvantaged:

The GF, ECSF, Treasure Foundation, TF and HFUS achieved these through training, capacity-building development and, advocacy.

Strategies in Executing the Strives and Impacts on the Disadvantaged:

Identification of the vulnerable people, taking their history, and follow-up (evaluation) are techniques adopted by the NGOs GF, ECSF, Treasure Foundation, TF, and HFUS to execute the impacts.

Efforts Reduction of the Rate of their Vulnerability:

The foundations acknowledge that every child and the majority of widows are vulnerable but the level of vulnerability differs. It has reduced crime rates such as minor rape, stealing, and alcohol addiction. The impacts have created jobs, increased the standard of living, and means of livelihood.

Disposition or Feedback of the Individual, Group of Individuals and the Communities to the Impacts of the NGO:

Call to appreciate the effort of the non-governmental organizations on a weekly, monthly and quarterly basis. An individual makes donations towards outreaches and campaigns. The government has recognized the NGOs' efforts with awards and recognition. While TF doesn't boarder about the feedback as regard her impacts on individuals and groups.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the reported results, it is concluded that the states give the non-governmental organizations a free hand to operate with policies backing them, to engage in societal problem-solving. The management and operations of charity organizations are dominated by the female gender. As social agents, the Goldheart Foundation, ECSF, Treasure Foundation, TF and HFUS through public participation have been able to bring succour and make provisions for the vulnerable, less-privileged and disadvantaged in society. In line with these, the social equity of sustainability which includes public participation to solve social problems has been achieved. Therefore, the study recommends more social agent participation in social arrangement and engagement. The male gender is encouraged to participate in humanitarian services.

Practical and Managerial Implications

The practical and managerial implications of this inquiry are: it will enable the government to institute more NGO-friendly policies, to continue to fill the gaps. The study will enable the wealthy class in society on the need to establish a foundation in other to join hands in combating social vices, injustice and imbalance.

AUTHORS' DECLARATIONS

Conceptualization, Aruleba T.J and Aruleba O.S; methodology, Aruleba T.J, Adeniyi B.C and Aruleba O.S; validation; Adeniyi B.C; formal analysis, Aruleba T.J; Investigation, Aruleba T.J, Adeniyi B.C and Aruleba O.S; resources; Aruleba T.J; data curation; Aruleba T.J and Adeniyi B.C; writing-original draft preparation; Aruleba T.J and Aruleba O.S; writing-review and editing, Aruleba T.J and Adeniyi B.C; funding

acquisition, Aruleba T.J, Adeniyi B.C and Aruleba O.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The qualitative data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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